

IMPACT FACTOR (UIF): 7.61
IMPACT FACTOR (SJIF): 7.61

ISSN: 2250-3811

TJPE

Thematics Journal of Physical Education

Informing scientific practices around the world through research and development

2022

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF FORMING STUDENTS' SENSE OF NATIONAL PRIDE IN EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: In this article, there described and specified broad concepts about the feeling of national pride. In particular, theoretical explanations were developed to strengthen the sense of national pride in students and young people through extracurricular activities.

Keywords: national pride, pride, intellectual, value, fortitude, glorious history, courage, character, national-cultural heritage, national value, science, honor, conscience, honesty, pride, epic, fairy tale, narrative, legend, proverb, riddle, parable.

Introduction.

In our country, special attention is being paid to the intellectual and spiritual potential inherited from our ancestors, rich culture, its preservation and enrichment, and on this basis, the issue of educating the young generation in the spirit of national and universal value. The content of such fundamental reforms is aimed at educating the young generation into a spiritually mature, physically healthy generation with intellectual potential. We all know that the role and importance of national pride in raising all-around mature youth is very high. This sets the task of further strengthening the scientific research work in the field, widening its scope and increasing its effectiveness.

This scientific work also serves to a certain extent to strengthen and provide performance of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Measures for the Development of Education and Science in the New Development Period of Uzbekistan" and "On measures to fundamentally improve the system of spiritual and educational affairs" [1; 2; 3].

The main part. "National pride is the material and spiritual heritage left by the ancestors, the contribution of one's people to the world civilization, the value in front of other nations, which is formed on the basis of the national self-awareness of an individual or a social group, a concept that expresses a sense of pride in value, prestige" [4].

National pride is a person's love for his homeland and people. It is a priceless blessing that glorifies the dignity, culture, enlightenment and identity of the nation. National pride is a characteristic that reflects the fortitude, glorious history, and bravery of each nation's great ancestors.

National pride is national identity that is a nation's conscious awareness that it is a unified social unit. National pride is a strong mental state, thanks to which historical unity, blood kinship, language, culture, spirituality, economic life and future unity take a deep place in the hearts of the representatives of the nation [5].

National pride is the feeling of patriotism, such as love for one's homeland, people, and awareness of one's belonging to a particular nation, expressed in the understanding of common interests, national culture, language and religion.

The activities organized in the classroom are aimed at increasing students' knowledge, forming a scientific worldview, and providing guidance for future career choices. The main purpose of extra-curricular activities is to provide students with knowledge, skills, and abilities, and to help them apply the acquired knowledge to life.

The main purpose and task of extracurricular activities is to improve the moral, labor, and aesthetic education of students. Extracurricular activities develop the student's ability, increase his enthusiasm for learning and create an opportunity for all-round development of his personality .

The importance of extracurricular activities:

- Making students learn the basics of science more deeply and forming their interest in science;
- Arming students with thorough and comprehensive knowledge;
- To develop the ability of independent and positive thinking in students;
- Giving students an important guide to consciously choosing a profession;
- Preparing students for life, creative work, defense of the homeland;
- Making students physically mature and spiritually mature;

Types of clubs that fully cover extracurricular activities:

- A) Scientific circles;
- B) Circles of skilled hands;
- C) Carpentry clubs;
- D) Sports comb;
- G) Artistic amateur club.

We have determined how effective it is for students to take the advantage of extracurricular activities. Among other things, we took the "Artistic amateur Club" as a basis from the types of clubs that the extracurricular activities cover. And we outlined the most important points and our own findings about it.

Recommendations developed for the formation of a sense of national pride in students in extracurricular activities:

- Honorable representatives of Uzbek people who showed a sense of national pride: Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdurauf Fitrat, Sadridin Aini, Fayzulla Khojaev, Obidjon Mahmudov, Ishaqkhan Ibrat, Bobookhun Salimov, An in-depth study of the

life and work of a number of our great ancestors, such as Baboniyoz Khoji Yusupov, Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, Abdulhamid Cholpon, Abdulla Qadiri, Abduqadir Shafuri, Abdulla Avloniy, Ubaidullahhoja Asadullahhojaev and Usman Nasir.

- Our national values honor knowledge, especially knowledge. "Kalila and Dimna" of the ancient Indian people, "Siyasatnama" of Nizamulmulk, "Saodatnama" of Nasir Khisrov, "Roshnama" of Yusuf Khos Hajib, "Kutadgu bilik" of Yusuf Khos Hajib about the fact that knowledge is the greatest wealth and there is nothing more valuable than it in the world. ", Ahmad Yugnaki's "Hibatul haqayyq", Ahmad Yassavi's "Devoni Hikmat", Alisher Navoi's "Khamsa", "Mahbub-ul Qulub" have important points. Reading these works and get the necessary and bright knowledge and interpretations.

- The scientific, artistic, historical, philosophical, medical, moral, jurisprudential and other works of our great grandfathers, poets, writers, scientists, who are highly knowledgeable in the culture and history of the Uzbek nation, have been making a worthy contribution to world civilization. Also, their great discoveries serve as the main factor in the formation of national pride of students. It is recommended to read and learn.

Studying Uzbek figures, national heroes and cultural heritage in forming a sense of national pride in students through extracurricular activities:

1. Representatives of classical Uzbek literature - Alisher Navoi, Hafiz Khorazmi, Haydar Khorazmi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Mirzo Bedil, Turdi Farog'iy, Makhmur, Munis Khorazmi, Boborahim Mashrab, Muhammad Reza Ogahi, Zakirjon Khalmuhammad's son Furqat, Muhammad Aminkhoja Muqimi, Muhammad Sharif Gulkhani, Kamil Khorazmi, Ahmad Donish, Avaz O'tar, Abdulla Qadiri, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulhamid Cholpon, Osman Nasir, as well as modern Uzbek literature in its place in the world literature Writers who make a worthy contribution to its existence are Gafur Ghulam, Mirtemir, Shuhrat, Hamid Olimjon. The works of Said Ahmad, Odil Yakubov, Pirimkul Kadyrov, Abdulla Oripov, Erkin Vahidov, O'tkir Hashimov, Shavkat Rahmon, Muhammad Yusuf and others are of particular importance in spreading the name of Uzbekistan to the world. At the same time, it is the basis for the further formation of the pride of students.

2. Courage of folk heroes. Along with legendary heroes such as Shiroq, To'maris, Spitamen, Abu Muslim, Muqanna, Temur Malik, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, generals, Najmuddin Kubro, Polatkhan, Qurbanjon Dodho, Dukchi Eshon, Madaminbek's guard, Shermuhammed's guard, Sabir Rahimov, Botir Boboev, Mamadali Topiboldiev, Akhmadjon Shukurov and others are examples for today's youth. Studying their activities encourages young people to love the Motherland, fight for its interests and sacrifice their lives.

3. National-cultural heritage. National values (customs, ceremonies and traditions), folklore, literature, science and art (folk crafts, national architecture, painting, singing, dance and art) Acquainting students with examples of national-cultural heritage such as other types of entertainment (cinema, theater, circus, national pottery) will help them to understand the characteristics of nationality, national lifestyle and national identity.

It is necessary to pay special attention to creating conditions for them to get to know the activities of athletes, bright representatives of Uzbek sports closely in order to raise the feeling of national pride of students such as Rufat Risqiev, Mikhail An, To'lagan Ishakov, Birodar Abduraimov, Mirjalal Kasimov, Azamat Abduraimov, Muhammadgadir Abdullaev, O'tkirbek Haydarov, Bahadir Sultanov, Artur Grigoryan . Bektemir Meliko'ziev, Rustam Tolaganov, Ruslan Nuriddinov, Rishod Sobirov, Dyorbek Orozboev, Elmurod Tasmurodov, Magomet Ibragimov, Ikhtiyor Navro'zov, Davlat Bobonov, Bekzod Abdurahmonov, Ulug'bek Rashidov, Akbar Joraev, Feruz Saidov , Parvina Samandarova, Dovurkhan Karomatov, Nafisa Sheripboeva, Nozimakhon Kayumova, Mohigul Khamdamova, Elbek Sultanov, Uchkun Kuronbaev, Asila Mirzayorova, Islam Aslanov and many others,. Organizing meetings with world-class athletes allows students to learn from them.

List of recommended literature to read and study in formation of national pride of students in extracurricular activities:

Use of examples of folklore:

1. Epics
2. Tales
3. Stories
4. Proverbs
5. Legends
6. Proverbs
7. Riddles
8. Proverbs

Using examples of classic literature:

1. "Bado'ul waqoe" (Zayniddin Muhammad Wasiqi)
2. "Khamsa" (Alisher Navoi)
3. "Yusuf and Zulayha" (Abdurahman Jami)
4. "G'aroyib – us sig'ar" (Alisher Navoi)
5. " Nazim – ul javoxir " (Alisher Navoi)
6. " Gul va navro'z " (Lutfiy) and others

Using examples of modern Uzbek literature:

1. "O't kishnagan oqshom" (Togay Murod)
2. "Yulduzlar mangu yonadi" (Togay Murod)
3. "So'nggi bekat" (Shukur Xolmirzayev)
4. "O'zbek polvonlari" (Tolqin Obidov)
5. "Otamdan qolgan dalalar" (Togay Murod)
6. "Osmonda yurgan odamlar" (Togay Murod)
7. "Oq qushlar oppoq qushlar" (Odil Yoqubov)

8. “Ulug‘bek xazinasi” (Odil Yoqubov)
9. “Uch ildiz” (Pirumqul Qodirov)
10. “Memos” (Pirumqul Qodirov)
11. “Olmos kamar” (Pirumqul Qodirov) and others

Recommendations on details that must be studied in the formation of national pride of students via extracurricular activities:

- Folk art
- Literature
- Science
- Art
- Folk crafts
- National architecture
- Painting
- National music and singing
- The art of dance
- Other types of art (cinema, theater, circus, national theater)
- Achievements in the field of production
- Family dynasty traditions
- Sports
- State symbols

Places of separate recognition of harmonious feelings together with the formation of students' national pride in extracurricular activities:

- Shame
- Honor
- Conscience
- Honesty
- Pride

Conclusion. In general, in the process of studying the topic of "national pride" during extracurricular activities, it became clear that the topic is more complex and comprehensive than we thought. It is clear to everyone that the concept of "national pride" includes dozens of qualities such as patriotism, courage, justice, honesty, brotherhood. While writing the article, we tried to focus on each of these qualities separately. In addition to the above recommendations, it was emphasized that it is important to memorize Muhammad Yusuf's poem "Muhammadqodir" in order to strengthen the sense of national pride in students. The importance of the narration

related to the work done by Pahlawan Mahmud in the land of Hind is extremely important in instilling a sense of patriotism in athletes. The path taken by Bo'ri the wrestler, the main character of the novel "Stars burn forever", is exemplary in all respects.

The heroes that inspire the students' spirituality and national pride in all the works included in the research were studied in connection with certain qualities, and important aspects were shown. And of course we hope that in the future we will contribute to the implementation of such large-scale works!

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